

Questionnaire for Seismic Vulnerability

The following questionnaire is a crucial phase of this study which has as main object the development of an integrated vulnerability tool addressing flood risk, seismic risk, landslide risk and building energy efficiency.

This tool should be able to indicate what the overall vulnerability of a building is, for the purpose of more effective management of interventions.

The developed methodology that can be valid for:

- residential building typology present in Algeria, and in particular for the area of the Wadi Abiod Valley;
- buildings with features similar to the one present in Algeria located in areas of the Globe subject to seismic, flood, and landslide risks, where targeted interventions for energy efficiency need to be implemented.

For the purpose of this assessment, individual vulnerabilities (called V_S , V_F , V_L , V_E in the diagram below) will first be assessed.

At the preliminary stage of the study, based on the relevant literature, the main factors affecting individual vulnerabilities toward seismic, flood, landslide risks and energy efficiency were identified. Then, these factors have been expertly grouped into categories.

With this questionnaire, we ask you, as experts, to give a weight to the individual vulnerability factors and categories that is representative of the factor or category importance in defining the total vulnerability of the building.

For clarity, the diagram below summarizes the steps identified for the individual vulnerability assessment.

Once the weights to each category and factor have been determined, the weight of the individual factor will be given by the product of the weight of the category and the weight of the factor within that category.

In particular, the individual vulnerability of the building (V_S , V_F , V_L , V_E) will be given by the following formula:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n P_i * \sum_{j=1}^m p_{i,j} * v_{i,j}$$

Where:

- P_i is the weight of the category i
- $p_{i,j}$ is the weight of the factor j within category i
- $v_{i,j}$ is the value of the factor j within category i (appropriately reclassified on a scale from 0 to 1)
- n is the total number of categories.
- m is the total number of factors within each category

Finally, the individual vulnerabilities for each risk will be integrated based on their respective hazards. This integration will allow for a comprehensive understanding of the building's overall vulnerability profile. The result can be used by decision-makers to prioritize mitigation efforts and allocate resources effectively to enhance the resilience of the building against various hazards.

Instructions for Questionnaire Completion

In what follows, you will first be provided with a description of the individual categories and the related factors identified for your risk. Then, you will be provided with an outline where you can provide your judgment and any comments and/or suggestions.

The following steps are recommended for completing the questionnaire:

1. First read the entire questionnaire, without thinking about assigning any values. This step serves to gain an overview of the problem in all its components.
2. Carefully reread the definitions of categories and factors.
3. Only then to associate a weight with each category (P_i), such that the sum of the category weights is equal to 1.
4. Next, we ask you to associate a weight ($p_{i,j}$) to the factors contained in each category, according to the criterion that within each category the sum of the weights should be equal to 1.

Note: in the COMMENTS section you should enter reason for choosing a weight value, whereas, in the SUGGESTIONS section you should enter eventual suggestions of any kind, including changes that you deem necessary (e.g., other factors to be considered, factors to be neglected, how the define the factor, etc...).

IT IS IMPORTANT THAT ANY CHOICES OR COMMENTS BE ARGUED, SO THAT THIS INFORMATION CAN BE PROVIDED TO THE POOL OF EXPERTS INVOLVED, WHO MAY MODIFY OR CONFIRM THEIR INITIAL JUDGMENT, AT A SECOND STAGE OF THE INVESTIGATION.

SEISMIC VULNERABILITY INDEX

Category 1: Structural characteristics of the building.

The structural characteristics of a building refer to its physical attributes and properties related to its construction and stability. Thus, the category "structural characteristics of the building" comprehensively represents all the vibration, design capacity and current capacity characteristics of the structure.

Weight Category 1 (P1)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

Category 2: Structural Regularity

This category contains all factors related to the presence or absence of structural regularity, in terms of planform configuration and elevation configuration. Note that regularity and symmetry are to be understood in terms of both mass distribution and stiffness distribution.

Weight Category 2 (P2)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

Category 3: Interventions that occurred during the life of the structure.

The last category refers to any modifications, repairs, or upgrades that have been implemented on the building over time. These interventions could include structural reinforcements, renovations, retrofitting for improved resilience against natural hazards, energy efficiency improvements, or any other alterations made to enhance the building's functionality, safety, or longevity.

Weight Category 3 (P3)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

Category 1: Structural characteristics of the building.

- **Height of the building**

Building height refers to the portion of the building above street level. It is an indicator for the vibration period of the structure.

Weight Factor 1 (p ₁₁)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Year of construction**

The year of construction is a factor that was considered because it is representative of both the state of wear and tear on the building and the regulatory framework in place at the time of design and construction.

Weight Factor 2 (p ₁₂)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Type of resisting system**

By type of resisting system is meant whether the structure is frame, resisting wall, mixed frame-wall structure, pendulum etc.

Weight Factor 3 (p ₁₃)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Roofing system**

Roofs are classified according to their action on the structure. Thus, one finds pushing, partially pushing and non-pushing roofs. In addition, another classification criterion is according to the weight of the roofing element.

Weight Factor 4 (p ₁₄)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Slab system**

The type of slab system can be classified on the basis of the horizontal structural system, which can be flexible, semi-rigid or rigid.

Weight Factor 5 (p ₁₅)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

Category 2: Structural Regularity

- **Planimetric configuration**

By plan configuration we mean whether the building is regular in plan or not. To this end, the distribution of stiffnesses must be approximately equal in the two orthogonal directions and the plan form is compact, i.e. there are no projecting elements or localized concavities.

Weight Factor 1 (p ₂₁)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Configuration in elevation**

The configuration in elevation, similarly to the configuration in plan, is an indicator of the regularity in elevation of the structure. In order to be considered regular in elevation, a building must fulfil the following conditions:

- no abrupt changes in the size of the storeys
- the stiffness of the columns must not be reduced by more than 30% and must not increase by more than 10%.
- no interruption or change in the resistance systems in elevation.

Weight Factor 2 (p ₂₂)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Maximum masonry spacing**

Maintaining proper spacing between masonry units is essential for enhancing the seismic resilience of a building. The masonry distance factor indicates whether the distance between walls of masonry buildings is less than 5m. In the case of non-masonry buildings, this factor defines the maximum ceiling span.

Weight Factor 3 (p23)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

Category 3: Interventions that occurred during the life of the structure.

- **Presence of seismic joints**

Seismic joints, also known as expansion joints or movement joints, are specialized features incorporated into buildings and structures to accommodate movement caused by seismic activity. These elements can be inserted at a later stage of construction.

Weight Factor 1 (p31)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Architectural components**

By architectural components we mean all those architectural elements that are not structural but have a significant mass, which can therefore be subject to earthquake-induced inertia forces. For this study we are going to classify architectural components as following:

- floors;
- furniture and contents, false ceiling;
- tiles and other roofing elements, windows and shutters;
- projecting elements, such as balconies and parapets, and masonry infill and cladding.

Weight Factor 2 (p32)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Plant components**

By this factor we mean the presence of plant components and their position within the structure, e.g.:

- installations whose accommodation was defined at the design stage;
- systems added after construction but positioned so as not to reduce the load-bearing capacity of the building;
- installations added after construction but positioned in such a way as to reduce the load-bearing capacity of the building.

Weight Factor 3 (p33)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **State of maintenance**

The state of maintenance in buildings refers to the condition and upkeep of various components and systems within a structure. The state of repair refers to the condition of the masonry, floors, windows, etc.

Weight Factor 4 (p34)	
Comments	
Suggestions	